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Research Article

**METHOD DEVELOPMENT AND VALIDATION OF
SIMULTANEOUS DETERMINATION OF FLUTAMIDE AND
AZATHIOPRINE BY USING RP-HPLC****Dharmasastha. S*, Gokulan P.D and K .L. Senthilkumar**Department of Pharmaceutical Analysis, Sri Vijay Vidyalyaya College of Pharmacy, Nallampalli,
Dharmapuri, Tamilnadu, India - 636807**Abstract:**

The aim of the work is to developing a specific, precise, accuracy, linear, simple, rapid, and validated and cost effective RP-HPLC method for the simultaneous estimation of these drugs in combined dosage forms. For the present study Azathioprine and Flutamide was selected. The separation was carried out by using mobile phase composition selected for the chromatographic separation of Azathioprine and Flutamide was acetonitrile and phosphate buffer of pH 2.3 in the ration of 45:55 v/v. The detection was carried out at 276 nm. The column was ODS Hypersil 5 μ C18, 4.6x250mm. The flow rate was selected as 1.0mL/min and Run time 25 Min. Diluent water: acetone (50:50) was used throughout the process.

The method was validated according to International Conference on Harmonization guidelines and successfully applied. The percentage of assay for Azathioprine and Flutamide was found to be 101.79% and 104.55% respectively. The percentage mean recovery of Azathioprine and Flutamide was found to be 99.43% and 99.53% respectively. The Developed method will be validated according to ICH guidelines and it can be used for routine analysis.

The precision for the developed method was found to be less than the maximum allowable limit percentage of relative standard deviation (%RSD) $\leq 2.0\%$.

The method was linear over the concentration range of 125.35- 376.05 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ for Azathioprine and 125.28-376.83 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ for Flutamide respectively. The method was found to be precise and suitable for the determination of Azathioprine and Flutamide by HPLC.

From the study and data it is concluded that, the method is found to be specific, Precise and Linear in the specified range. System suitability is established and recorded. Hence, this method can be used for routine analysis for determination of Azathioprine and Flutamide by RP-HPLC

KEYWORDS: HPLC, Azathioprine and Flutamide, Quantitative estimation.

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INTRODUCTION:

Azathioprine Synthesized originally as a cancer drug and a prodrug for mercaptopurine in 1957, it has been widely used as an immunosuppressant for more than 50 years. Azathioprine acts as a pro drug for mercaptopurine, inhibiting an enzyme that is required for the synthesis of DNA. Thus it most strongly affects proliferating cells, such as the T cells and B cells of the immune system. Azathioprine, is chemically 6-(1- methyl-4-nitroimidazole-5-yl) thiopurine, is an immunosuppressive agent. They are used in the chemotherapy of acute leukemia, for immunosuppressant after solid-organ transplantation, and increasingly for immunomodulation in autoimmune disease. Currently, AZA is standard treatment in patients with chronically active inflammatory bowel disease (IBD). Azathioprine acts on several modes in cellular immunity processes. It inhibits lymphocyte activation, lymphocyte differentiation, in vitro lymphocyte stimulation, and in vitro mixed lymphocyte reaction and it reduces the activity of natural killer lymphocytes^(1- 5).

Flutamide is an acetanilide, nonsteroidal compound with orally active antiandrogenic properties. It exerts its antiandrogenic action by inhibiting androgen uptake and/ or nuclear binding of androgen in target tissues. It is used, usually with gonadorelin analogues; in the palliative treatment of prostatic carcinoma. It is freely soluble in Acetone, Ethyl acetate, Methyl alcohol⁽⁶⁻⁸⁾.

For the present study Azathioprine and Flutamide was selected. The extensive literature survey carried out revealed that there is no method reported for the simultaneous estimation of these drugs and some methods for estimation of individual drug by HPLC and spectrophotometer are available. Hence present study aim to developing a specific, precise, accuracy, linear, simple, rapid, and validated and cost effective RP-HPLC method for the simultaneous estimation of these drugs in combined dosage forms.

MATERIALS AND METHOD:

Chemicals and reagent

HPLC Water- Milli-Q grade, Acetonitrile- Fisher scientific, Methanol- Fisher scientific, Potassium di hydrogen phosphate- Merck, Ortho phosphoric

acid- Sigma, Hydrochloric acid- Merck. These solvents were used throughout method development and validation Drug samples were obtained from the Global pharma Pvt Ltd. The purity of these components was confirmed from the monographs in pharmacopoeias and reported methods.

Instrumentation

The HPLC method development and validation was done using Waters Acquity EMPOWER. With Quaternary pump and UV/PDA system. The UV-Visible spectrophotometer -Perkin elmer, Analytical balance PICO and Vacuum Oven from Lab India

Solubility:

Azathioprine is soluble in organic solvents such as ethanol, DMSO, and dimethyl formamide, which should be purged with an inert gas. The solubility of Azathioprine in these solvents is approximately 10 and 20 mg/ml. Azathioprine is sparingly soluble in aqueous buffers. According to literature review Flutamide is very slightly soluble in acetonitrile and soluble in chloroform and dichloromethane, and it is practically insoluble (0.002%) in water. Finally buffer pH2.3, Ethanol and Acetonitrile in the ratio of 100:100:300 was selected as a solvent.

Selection of Mobile phase:

The pure drugs Azathioprine and Flutamide were injected in combination in the ratio of their contents in the formulation to the chromatographic system, and run in different mobile phase compositions. Different mobile phases containing different compositions of methanol: water, acetonitrile: water, acetonitrile: Phosphate buffer 6.8 and acetonitrile: Phosphate buffer pH. 2.3 was tried for the selection of optimum conditions for the simultaneous determination of Azathioprine and Flutamide. It was found that optimal separation of the two components was achieved with acetonitrile and phosphate buffer, compared to other mobile phases. Different ratios of the selected mobile phase were tried with varying flow rates and pH. Finally, the mobile phase composition selected for the chromatographic separation of Azathioprine and Flutamide was acetonitrile and phosphate buffer of pH 2.3 in the ration of 45:55 v/v (Table No 1).

Table 1.Optimized Chromatographic condition:

Mobile phase	Acetonitrile: ortho phosphoric acid (550:450)
Flow rate	1ml/min
Column	ODS Hypersil 5 μ C18,4.6 \times 250mm
Detector wavelength	UV, 254nm
Column temperature	25 °C
Injection volume	20 μ L
Run time	15min
Result	Two peaks are separated well with good resolution

Validation

Validation studies were performed as per ICH guidelines⁽⁸⁻⁹⁾. All the test results were calculated by appropriate statistical methods and all the test results complied with standard limits.

1. Accuracy
2. Specificity
3. Linearity
4. Precision
5. Assay
6. LOD
7. LOQ
8. System suitability

System Suitability:

System suitability is the test to ensure that the methods can generate results of acceptable accuracy and precision. They also be verified that the analytical system is worked properly and can give accurate and precise results.

Procedure:

Injected 10 μ L separately each of the Blank and Standard based on the injection sequence given in (Table No 2).

Table 2: HPLC Injection profile for System suitability

Solutions	Number of Injections
Blank	1
Standard Solution	6

Specification Limits:

Each mL Contains Azathioprine In %:- Not less than 90.0 % and not more than 110.0 % Each mL Contains Flutamide In %:- Not less than 90.0 % and not more than 110.0 %.

Specificity:

Specificity is the ability of analytical method to assess unequivocally the analyte in the presence of component that may be expected to be present, such as impurities, degradation products and matrix components.

Standard solution Preparation:

Standard stock A: 0.5 mg/mL of Azathioprine is prepared in by transfer 50 mg of standard in 50 ml volumetric flask. Add 50 % of mobile phase to the flask and sonicate well. Dilute with mobile phase to volume up. Standard stock B: 0.5 mg/mL of Flutamide is prepared by transfer 50 mg of standard in 50 ml volumetric flask. Add 50 % of mobile phase to the flask and sonicate well. Dilute with mobile phase to volume up.

Standard solution:

Transfer 5ml of Standard stock A and 5ml of Standard stock B in 20 ml flask and sonicate well and make up with mobile phase.

Injection profile:

Injected 20 μ L separately each of the following solutions into the HPLC. The injection profiles given in the (Table No 3)

Table 3 : HPLC Injection profile for Specificity

Solutions	Number of Injections
Blank (mobile phase)	1
Standard Solution	1

Acceptance criteria:

There should be no interfering peak in the chromatogram at the retention time corresponding to the peak of Azathioprine and Flutamide.

Precision:

The precision of an analytical method is the degree of agreement among individual test results when the method is applied repeatedly to multiple sampling of homogeneous sample the precision of analytical method is usually expressed as the standard deviation or relative standard deviation (Coefficient of variation) of series of measurements.

System Precision:

The system precision checked by using standard chemical substance to ensure that the analytical system is working properly. The retention time and area response of six determinations should be

measured and calculate relative standard deviation.

Procedure:

Injected 20 μ L separately each of the blank and standard solutions into the HPLC. The injection profile is given in the (Table No 4).

Table 4: HPLC Injection profile for System precision

Solutions	Number of Injections
Blank (mobile phase)	1
Standard Solution	6

Acceptance criteria:

The RSD of Retention time for Azathioprine and Flutamide peak obtained from 6 injections of Standard Solution should be NMT 1 %.

The RSD of Area Response for Azathioprine and Flutamide peak obtained from 6 injections of Standard Solution should be NMT 2 %.

- Tailing factor for Azathioprine and Flutamide peak should be not more than 2.0
- RSD Azathioprine peak in standard solution should not be more than 2.0%.

Linearity:

Linearity is the measure of how well a calibration plot of response Vs concentration approximates a straight line. Linearity can be assessed by performing the single measurement s at several analyte concentrations. The data are then processed using a linear least square regression. The resulting plot slope, intercept and correlation coefficient provide the desired information on linearity. Ability to obtain test results which are directly proportional to the concentration of analyte. For an establishment of the linearity 50%, 80%, 100%, 120%, and 150% of standard and sample concentrations shall be used

Preparation of Standard solutions

Standard stock A: 0.5 mg/mL of Azathioprine is prepared in by transfer 50 mg of standard in 50 ml volumetric flask. Add 50 % of mobile phase to the flask and sonicate well. Dilute with mobile phase to volume up.

Standard stock B: 0.5 mg/mL of Flutamide is prepared by transfer 50 mg of standard in 50 ml volumetric flask. Add 50 % of mobile phase to the flask and sonicate well. Dilute with mobile phase to volume up. Standard solution: Transfer 5ml of Standard stock A and 5ml of Standard stock B in 20 ml flask and sonicate well and make up with mobile phase.

Linearity solution 50% level: Weigh accurately 2.5 ml of Standard stock A and 2.5 ml of Standard stock B in 20 ml flask and sonicate well and make

up with mobile phase.

Linearity solution 80% level: Weigh accurately 4ml of Standard stock A and 4 ml of Standard stock B in 20 ml flask and sonicate well and make up with mobile phase.

Linearity solution 100% level: Weigh accurately 5ml of Standard stock A and 5ml of Standard stock B in 20 ml flask and sonicate well and make up with mobile phase.

Linearity solution 120% level: Weigh accurately 6 ml of Standard stock A and 6 ml of Standard stock B in 20 ml flask and sonicate well and make up with mobile phase.

Linearity solution 150% level: Weigh accurately 7.5 ml of Standard stock A and 7.5 ml of Standard stock B in 20 ml flask and sonicate well and make up with mobile phase.

Injection Profile: Injected 10 μ L of the Blank and Standard solution as per the (Table No 5)

Table 5: HPLC Injection profile for Linearity Acceptance Criteria:

Sl.No	Solution Name	No. of Injections
1.	Blank	1
2.	Standard solution	6
3.	Linearity solution 50%	3
4.	Linearity solution 80%	3
5.	Linearity solution 100%	3
6	Linearity solution 120%	3
7	Linearity solution 150%	3

Correlation Coefficient and Regression Coefficient for Azathioprine and Flutamide should be NLT 0.99.

Assay

Standard solution Preparation:

Standard stock A: 0.5 mg/mL of Azathioprine is prepared in by transfer 50 mg of standard in 50 ml volumetric flask. Add 50 % of mobile phase to the flask and sonicate well. Dilute with mobile phase to volume up.

Standard stock B: 0.5 mg/mL of Flutamide is prepared by transfer 50 mg of standard in 50 ml volumetric flask. Add 50 % of mobile phase to the flask and sonicate well. Dilute with mobile phase to volume up.

Standard solution: Transfer 5ml of Standard stock A and 5ml of Standard stock B in 20 ml flask and sonicate well and make up with mobile phase.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION:

A simple Reverse phase high performance liquid chromatographic method has been developed and subsequently validated for Azathioprine and Flutamide.

The separation was carried out by using mobile phase composition selected for the chromatographic separation of Azathioprine and Flutamide was acetonitrile and phosphate buffer of pH 2.3 in the

ration of 45:55 v/v. The detection was carried out at 276 nm. The column was ODS Hypersil 5 μ C18, 4.6x250mm. The flow rate was selected as 1.0mL/min.

System Suitability

Table 6: Area of response of 6 standard injections in HPLC for system suitability

Standard Injection	Area Response For Azathioprine(mAU)	Area Response For Flutamide (mAU)
1	16206	13988
2	16251	14022
3	16221	14501
4	16222	14003
5	16230	14005
6	16240	14017
Average	16219	14085
STDEV	15.667	204.026
%RSD	0.09	1.44

Table 7: Results for system suitability parameter

S.NO	Acceptance Criteria	RESULT
1	%RSD for Area of Azathioprine and Flutamide peak in standard solution should not be more than 2.0%.	0.09 & 1.44

Chromatogram of Blank Solution

Peak Table

Name	Ret. Time	Area	Area%	Type

Chromatogram for Standard solution (System Suitability)

Peak Table
PDA Ch1 Absorbance (254nm +/- 4nm) (+)

Name	Ret. Time	Area	Area%	Type	USP Tailing	Resolution
Flutamide	6.010	13988	47.4347	BB	0.98	-
Azathioprine	8.955	16206	52.5653	BB	1.12	6.23
		66346043	100.000			

Discussion for System Suitability

System suitability result passes with reference to the table 6 & 7 the results obtained for System Suitability are found within the acceptance criteria. The obtained results proved that there will not be blank interference in the Azathioprine and Flutamide peak by this method. The chromatograms were showed in Chromatogram 2 to 3.

Specificity

Table 8: Specificity system suitability report

S.NO	Parameters	Results Obtained		Acceptance Criteria
		Azathioprine	Flutamide	
1	Tailing factor from five replicate injections	0.98	1.12	NMT 2.0
2	% RSD of area for five standard injection	0.09	1.44	NMT 2.0 %
3	Resolution between Azathioprine and Flutamide	6.23		NLT 5.0

Table 9: Acceptance criteria

S.NO	ACCEPTANCE CRITERIA	RESULT
1	There should be no interfering peak in the chromatogram at the retention time corresponding to the peak of Azathioprine and Flutamide	Complies

Discussion for Specificity

Specificity result passes with reference to the table 8 and 9 the results obtained for Specificity are found within the acceptance criteria. The obtained results proved that there will not be blank interference in the Azathioprine and Flutamide peak by this method.

Precision**Table 10: Area response and retention time of 5 standard injections for system precision**

Standard Injection	Area response for Azathioprine (mAU)	Retention time for Azathioprine (min)	Area response for Flutamide (mAU)	Retention time for Flutamide (min)
1	16206	2.970	13988	8.048
2	16197	2.788	13996	8.047
3	16221	2.790	14501	8.050
4	16222	2.787	14003	8.047
5	16230	2.789	14005	8.046
6	16240	2.787	14017	8.045
Average	16219	2.8185	14085	8.0471
STDEV	15.667	0.0074	204.026	0.002

Table 11: Acceptance criteria for system Precision

S.NO	ACCEPTANCE CRITERIA	RESULT	
		Azathioprine	Flutamide
1	1.The RSD of the Retention time for Azathioprine and Flutamide peak obtained from 6 injections of Standard Solution should be NMT 1 %.	0.2	0.02
2	2.The RSD of the Area response for Azathioprine and Flutamide peak obtained from 6 injections of Standard Solution should be NMT 2 %.	0.09	1.44

Discussion for System Precision

All the System Precision parameters were well within the desirable limits with reference to the table 10 & 11 it indicates that the prescribed method is suitable to perform the estimation of Azathioprine and Flutamide. The chromatograms were showed in the chromatogram figure 7 to 9

Linearity**Linearity of Azathioprine****Table 12: Area response linearity solutions of Azathioprine**

	RUN 1	RUN 2	RUN 3	MEAN
50 %	8591	8593	8592	8592
80 %	13477	13477	13494	13483
100 %	16252	16264	16250	16255
120 %	18784	18793	18767	18781
150 %	21503	21479	21430	21471

Table 13: Concentration vs Area response of linearity solution of Azathioprine

	Concentration	Mean area
50%	125.35	8592
80%	200.56	13483
100%	250.70	16255
120%	300.84	18781
150%	376.05	21471
	Slope	51.573
	Intercept	2786.974713
	Correlation coefficient R²	0.991930972

Linearity Graph for Azathioprine:

The Linearity graph of Azathioprine for concentration of solution and area response is shown in the figure 10

Linearity of Flutamide

Table 14: Area response of linearity solutions of Flutamide

	RUN 1	RUN 2	RUN 3	MEAN
50%	7134	7136	7137	7136
80%	11353	11355	11373	11360
100%	14022	14021	14022	14022
120%	16950	16960	16951	16954
150%	21113	21122	21103	21113

Table 15: Concentration vs area response of linearity solution of Flutamide

	Concentration	Mean area
50%	125.28	7136
80%	200.44	11360
100%	250.55	14022
120%	300.66	16954
150%	376.83	21113
	Slope	55.567
	Intercept	3.13196541
	Correlation coefficient R²	0.999943642

Linearity Graph For Flutamide:

The Linearity graph of Flutamide for concentration of solution and area response is shown in the figure 11

Table 16: Acceptance criteria for linearity

S.NO	ACCEPTANCE CRITERIA	RESULT	
		AZATHIOPRINE	BICALUTAMI DE
1	Correlation Coefficient and for Azathioprine and Flutamide Should be NLT 0.99.	0.991930972	0.999943642

Discussion for linearity

Linearity result passes and the results obtained for linearity are found within the acceptance criteria with reference to the table 12 to 16. Hence it is concluded that the range of concentrations, 50 % to 150 % with respect to 100% working concentration for assay method is linear for Azathioprine and Flutamide.

Assay**Assay for Azathioprine**

Table 17: Assay for Azathioprine

S.No	Name	Retention Time	Area
1	Standard	2.788	16206
2	Standard	2.790	16221
3	Standard	2.786	16230
4	Standard	2.785	16240

	RUN 1	RUN 2	RUN 3	MEAN	%RECOVERY	% of Mean Recovery
50 %	8591	8593	8592	8592	99.23%	99.43%
100%	16252	16264	16250	16255	99.42%	
150%	21503	21479	21430	21471	99.65%	

Assay for Flutamide

Table 18: Assay for Flutamide

S.No	Name	Retention Time	Area
1	Standard	8.850	13988
2	Standard	8.047	13953
3	Standard	8.046	13746
4	Standard	8.045	13887

	RUN 1	RUN 2	RUN 3	MEAN	%RECOVERY	% of Mean Recovery
50%	7134	7136	7137	7136	99.20%	99.53%
100%	14022	14021	14022	14022	99.56%	
150%	21113	21122	21103	21113	99.85%	

No. Of Runs	Name	Result For Azathioprine	Result For Flutamide
Run 1	Standard	102.36 %	96.25 %
Run 2	Standard	105.56 %	108.54 %
Run 3	Standard	100.98 %	102.45 %
Run 4	Standard	98.26 %	108.98 %
Mean		101.79 %	104.55 %
% RSD		0.09 %	1.44 %

Figure 17: Chromatogram of HPLC for Assay

Acceptance Criteria:**For Azathioprine:**

Not less than 90.0 % and not more than 110.0 %

For Flutamide:

Not less than 90.0 % and not more than 110.0 %.

TABLE 23: ACCEPTANCE CRITERIA FOR ASSAY

S.NO	ACCEPTANCE CRITERIA	RESULT	
		AZATHIOPRINE	FLUTAMIDE
1	The result should be within the specified limit	Complies	Complies
2	The RSD calculation for Azathioprine and Flutamide should be NMT 2.0 %	0.09 %	1.44 %

Limit of Quantitation (LOQ)**Table 24: Limit of Quantitation (LOQ)**

Injection	Peak area for Azathioprine	Peak area for Flutamide
1	16206	13988
2	16197	14022
3	16221	14501
4	16222	14003
5	16230	14005
6	16204	14017
Mean	16213	14085
LOQ	0.065	0.018

Limit of Detection (LOD)**Table 25: Limit of Detection (LOD)**

Injection	Peak area for Azathioprine	Peak area for Flutamide
1	2970	8048
2	2788	8047
3	2790	8050
4	2787	8047
5	2789	8046
6	2787	8045
Mean	2818	8047
LOD conc.	0.08	0.004

Discussion for LOD and LOQ

All the LOD and LOQ parameters were well within the desirable limits with reference to the table 24 and 25. It indicates that the prescribed method is suitable to perform the estimation of Azathioprine and Flutamide

CONCLUSION:

After a thorough literature survey, it was found that there is no suitable chromatographic method available for the quantitative analysis of Azathioprine and Flutamide. Thus, we have decided to develop a simple, precise, accurate, economical chromatographic method for the determination of Azathioprine and Flutamide by RPHPLC. A simple, rapid, precise, accurate and reproducible, HPLC method has been developed for the quantitative analysis of Azathioprine and Flutamide. An isocratic separation was achieved using a ODS Hypersil C18 column in the Size of 4.6×250mm with 5 µm particle size at the temperature of 25°C with a flow rate of 1.0 ml/min and UV detector at 276 nm.

The Buffer consist of 2.96 g/L of potassium dihydrogen phosphate and 0.576 g/L dipotassium hydrogen phosphate in water, and adjust with ortho-phosphoric acid to a pH 3.2±0.1. The mobile phase consisted of Buffer: Acetonitrile (50:50v/v). The retention time for Azathioprine and Flutamide was found to be 2.789min and 8.047 min respectively.

The method was developed for specificity, Precision, Accuracy, Linearity, Assay, LOD, and LOQ. The specificity of the method was determined by assessing no interfering peaks in the chromatogram at the retention time corresponding to the peak of Azathioprine and Flutamide.

The precision for the developed method was found to be less than the maximum allowable limit percentage of relative standard deviation (%RSD) ≤ 2.0%. The method was linear over the concentration range of 125.35- 376.05µg/ml (cc = 0.991930972) for Azathioprine and 125.28-376.83 µg/ml (cc=0.999943642) for Flutamide respectively. The method was found to be precise and suitable for the determination of Azathioprine and Flutamide by HPLC. System suitability is established and recorded.

The LOD concentration for Azathioprine and Flutamide was found to be 0.08 µg/ml and 0.004 µg/ml respectively. The LOQ concentration for Azathioprine and Flutamide was found to be 0.0065 µg/ml and 0.018 µg/ml respectively. The percentage of assay for Azathioprine and Flutamide was found to be 101.79% and 104.55% respectively. The percentage mean recovery of Azathioprine and Flutamide was found to be 99.43% and 99.53% respectively. The Developed method will be validated according to ICH guidelines and it can be used for routine analysis.

From the study and data it is concluded that, the method is found to be specific, Precise and Linear in the specified range. System suitability is established and recorded. Hence, this method can be used for routine analysis for determination of Azathioprine and Flutamide by RP-HPLC.

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